

A Deep Learning Loss Based on Additive Cosine Margin: Application to Fashion Style and Face Recognition

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Abstract

Recently, loss functions based on angular spans improved the performance of deep visual recognition. These losses converted Euclidean cross entropy to angular cross entropy loss. Fashion style recognition deals with the problem of assigning a person's outfit to a fashion style category. Due to the high similarity between different clothing items and the use of softmax-based loss functions, many of the current methods that address this problem show relatively poor performance and cannot guarantee sufficient inter-class margins in the fashion domain. In this work, we propose an end-to-end method for deep visual recognition by combining a standard CNN architecture with a novel loss function, which we call Additive Cosine Margin Loss (ACML). The proposed function not only projects feature vectors of different classes into different regions of the embedding, but also enforces compactness of the projections within each class. Our experiments were conducted on two public and well-known fashion style recognition datasets FashionStyle14 and HipsterWars, and on the face verification and identification datasets LFW, YTF, and MegaFace. These experiments demonstrate the superiority of the proposed loss function over: 1) existing angular margin-based loss functions 2) state-of-the-art methods for clothing style recognition as well as face analysis tasks.

Keywords: Deep learning, Classification, Angular margin-based loss function, Compactness and separability, Deep fashion style recognition, Deep face recognition.

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1 Introduction

The use of computer vision techniques for automatic analysis of clothing images has attracteded increasing attention in the research community. In this context, clothing retrieval [1, 22, 12], clothing attribute classification [44, 47, 2, 19, 32, 18] and understanding-based tasks [3, 50, 27, 43] are some of the topics that can be considered in *eye of the hurricane*. Among all, fashion style recognition is particularly important [48], mainly because it is an important component of automated fashion recommendation systems to offer suitable products based on fashion styles. Fashion style recognition can help fashion designers to check if their products are suitable for target fashion styles or not. It helps people to search for fashion items according to keywords without making manual annotations. Another application is the automated tracking of fashion trends using online and customer images. Clothing style recognition is still a challenging task because the clothing images of the same style may have diverse textures, colors, and fabric characteristics, deceiving the system in style recognition. In addition, the garments in the images are often subject to deformation and occlusion, which also makes fashion style recognition difficult. The softmax loss used by Deep Learning based classification models is not very robust when a small perturbation occurs in the data, which significantly affects the classification performance. In recent years, many approaches have focused on loss functions to increase discriminative power, which aims to reduce the variations within a class and increase the variations between classes. To improve the discriminative power of Softmax, SphereFace [23], AM-Softmax [41, 42] and ArcFace [5] reformulated Softmax on the angle space and introduces margin constraints to increase inter-class distances and reduce intra-class variations.

AM-Softmax puts more emphasis on extending inter-class distances, while ArcFace improves compactness within classes. AM-Softmax increases inter-class distance by adding the cosine margin, while ArcFace moves the additive cosine margin into angle space to enhance intra-class compactness by penalising the target logit. Thus, intra-class compactness and inter-class diversity do not occur simultaneously. AM-Softmax sets a rough margin to separate the feature vectors of different classes, it often

happens that the intra-class distances are not small enough compared to the inter-class distances.

60 Despite the good results that angular margin-based Softmax losses have achieved in recent years, their performance depends on the best margin, which is difficult to predict and fine-tune between different sets of values. However, the best margin depends on the problem. This means that the best margin for the face recognition problem would not be suitable for style recognition. Moreover, choosing an inappropriate margin leads
65 to increased intra-class variance and misclassification.

In this research, to jointly enforce inter-class separation and intra-class compactness, we add an additive angle mini-margin to the target angle associated with the cosine margin to formulate a novel loss function called additive cosine margin loss (ACML) for deep fashion style recognition. After normalising features and weights,
70 the dot product between the CNN features and the last fully connected layer provides the cosine distance. First, a cosine margin penalty is added to the target logit to distinguish inter-class distances. Then, the arc cosine function is used to calculate the angle between the current feature and the target weight from the distinguished target logit. We add an additive angular mini-margin (like Arface loss) to the distinguished
75 target angle to improve the compactness within the class. Then, we back-calculate the target logit by applying the cosine function on the resulting angle. Finally, we rescale all logits with a fixed feature norm and follow exactly the same steps as for softmax loss. ACML shows better performance in learning a feature representation that maps similar styles as close as possible and dissimilar styles as far apart as possible. The
80 contributions of this study are summarized as follows.

1. By adding an additive angular mini-margin to the recomputed target angle, we enhance the discriminative power of the deeply learned features and stabilise the training process.
2. ACML draws features of the same class as close as possible, while increasing the
85 distances between features of different classes. Both theoretical and empirical studies confirm the effectiveness of ACML.
3. Extensive experiments on style and face recognition tasks support the effective-

ness of the proposed method.

This paper is organized in the following sections. Section 2 presents the main notations used and discusses some related works. The formal description of our method is given in Section 3. Experiments and results are described in Section 4, while Section 5 concludes the article.

Table 1: Definition of the main notations used in this article.

Symbol	Description
N	Number of batch size
C	Number of classes
\mathbf{x}_i	The deep features of the i -th sample
\mathbf{w}_{y_i}	The ground truth weight vector of class y_i
$\mathbf{w}_j \in \mathbb{R}^{d \times C}$	The j -th column (j -th class) of the weight $\mathbf{W} \in \mathbb{R}^{d \times C}$
θ_{y_i}	The angle between the weight \mathbf{w}_{y_i} and the feature \mathbf{x}_i
θ_{t_i}	The corresponding angle between the feature \mathbf{x}_i and the distinct ground truth weight
m	Additive inter-class margin penalty
m^*	Additive intra-class angular mini-margin penalty
s	The feature scale to multiply all logits

2 Related Work

2.1 Notations

In this paper, to unify the mathematical elements, we have stylized the notation. The large capital letters represent the matrices and the small capital letters represent the vectors. \mathbf{x}_i is the deep features of the i -th sample. The j -th column of the weight matrix \mathbf{W} is denoted as $\mathbf{w}_j \in \mathbb{R}^{d \times C}$, where d is the dimension of the samples and C is the number of classes. m and m^* represent the inter-class margin and intra-class mini-margin, respectively. θ_{y_i} represents the angle between the weight \mathbf{w}_{y_i} and the feature \mathbf{x}_i , while θ_{t_i} represents the corresponding angle between the feature \mathbf{x}_i and the distinct ground truth weight. s is a feature scale to multiply all logits (See Table 1).

2.2 Clothing Style Recognition

Several studies have been conducted on the recognition of fashion style. Kiapour et al. [17] have created the dataset HipsterWars. This dataset consists of 1,893 images related to five fashion styles: Bohemian, Goth, Hipster, Pinup, and Preppy. To

indicate the strength of reflection of each fashion style by an image, each image has been assigned a confidence score of 0 to 50. The classifications and confidence scores were determined by user voting. Using a hand-crafted feature extraction technique
110 with a support vector machine (SVM) classifier, they classified the images, but did not achieve such high accuracy. Then, Deep Learning-based approaches were used to classify fashion styles[37, 33, 25, 13, 15, 24, 40, 28]. Takagi et al. [37] collected the FashionStyle14 dataset. This dataset consists of 13,126 images related to 14 fashion styles: conservative, dressy, ethnic, fairy, feminine, gal, girlish, casual, lolita, mode,
115 natural, retro, rock, and street. The styles are annotated by fashion experts. They performed comparative experiments with different fine-tuned CNNs (ResNet50, VGG19, Xception, Inception v3, and VGG16) for classification. Simo-Serra et al. [33] proposed an architecture called StyleNet which is based on the Siamese network with a weakly supervised deep learning technique. They used a distance-based triplet ranking loss to
120 provide discriminative features that maximize the dissimilar distance and minimize the similar distance. Their proposed framework achieved best performance compared to previous methods, but since distance-based ranking loss requires a lot of data for training, their framework had some limitations. Nakajima et al. [25] proposed a method that utilizes the capabilities of CNNs in feature extraction and detecting the human area in
125 a pixel unit through semantic segmentation. They used the well-known pre-trained ResNet50 architecture for feature extraction, Single Shot Multibox Detector (SSD) for human areas detection, Pyramid Scene Parsing Network (PSPNet) for human body semantic segmentation, and SVM for classification. Due to the lack of sufficient data for training, PSPNet was trained using the PASCAL VOC dataset, which results in
130 lower performance. Jiang et al. [15] attempted to centralize each feature of a certain style using a consensus style centralizing auto-encoder (CSCAE) to improve feature learning. To this end, weak style features were gradually drawn to the center of the class. Then, the weights for the different style features were automatically assigned by the consensus column constraints. However, the assignment of the weights of the
135 different columns before minimizing the cost function was done manually. Inspired by Bimodal Deep Autoencoder, Ma et al. [24] introduced a fashion-oriented multi-modal deep learning model called Bimodal Correlative Deep Autoencoder (BCDA) to

capture the correlation between visual features and fashion styles. To describe fashion styles universally and quantitatively, they created a Fashion Semantic Space (FSS) based on Kobayashi’s aesthetics theory using the words people typically use to describe fashion styles on shopping websites. To implement the task of mapping visual features to FSS, BCDA connects with regression models. The BCDA learns the basic rules of tops and bottoms as two modals of clothing collocations to generate input to the regression model for predicting coordinate values in the FSS. Vaccaro et al. [40] presented a data-driven fashion model that translates low-level design elements (e.g., “red cardigan,” “lightweight shirt”) into high-level styles (e.g., “valentines day”) by training polylingual topic modeling on outfit data collected from Polyvore. This model attempts to translate between languages through the topic space by using a natural language processing technique to learn latent fashion concepts jointly over style and element vocabularies. In contrast to previous studies that aimed at supervised style classification, Hsiao et al. [13] discovers the underlying elements of style by exploring style-coherent representation, as opposed to manually defining them. They proposed an unsupervised learning method based on polylingual thematic models to learn the composition of clothing from visual features that are stylistically similar. The different elements of fashion design and their relationships to each other result in a variety of fashion styles. Since different styles are similar in some poses and lighting variability, the main problem in understanding fashion styles is how to extract discriminative features for different styles. We address the representation of discriminative features for fashion style recognition by proposing a novel loss function that maps images with similar styles as close as possible and images with dissimilar styles as far apart as possible.

2.3 Loss Functions

In Deep Learning, loss functions play an important role in deciding the type of features that should be preferred in a typical learning task and largely determine the performance of a neural network. In the most common CNN architectures designed for classification tasks, learning is performed using softmax loss. However, it is well known that this loss has low robustness. Even relatively small perturbations in the data

often lead to remarkable changes in the resulting class boundaries, which significantly reduces the classification performance. To promote better discriminative performance, some methods combine the softmax loss with the contrastive loss [30], the center loss [45, 52], and the triplet loss [9, 7, 10] to enhance intra-class compactness and inter-class dispersion in Euclidean space. Both contrastive loss and triplet loss cannot be restricted to each sample and require a carefully designed pair/triplet mining procedure, which is both time consuming and performance dependent. On the other hand, the features learned by softmax loss have an intrinsic angular distribution, combining Euclidean margin-based loss with softmax loss to construct joint supervision is not well motivated to enhance the discriminative power of the features. To address this issue, several authors have attempted to reformulate softmax loss by imposing constraints to increase inter-class distances and reduce intra-class variations. SphereFace [23, 34, 8] improved angular discrimination by using a multiplicative angular margin. They moved the angle space to cosine space by using the definition of the inner product between feature vectors and corresponding weights in Softmax. They set the bias terms to zero, normalized the weights in the forward propagation stage, and added a margin to the angle to obtain the ASoftmax loss as follows:

$$L_{\text{ASoftmax}} = -\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \log \frac{e^{\|\mathbf{x}_i\| \psi(\theta_{y_i})}}{e^{\|\mathbf{x}_i\| \psi(\theta_{y_i})} + \sum_{j=1, j \neq y_i}^C e^{\|\mathbf{x}_i\| \cos(\theta_j)}} \quad (1)$$

in which they define $\psi(\theta_{y_i}) = (-1)^k \cos(m \theta_{y_i}) - 2k$, $\theta_{y_i} \in \left[\frac{k\pi}{m}, \frac{(k+1)\pi}{m} \right]$ and $k \in [0, m-1]$. \mathbf{x}_i is the learned feature vector corresponding to the ground-truth label y_i and θ_{y_i} is the angle between normalized vector \mathbf{w}_j and \mathbf{x}_i . $m \geq 1$ is an integer that controls the size of angular margin. Since m is limited to a positive integer instead of a real number, the margin is not flexible enough.

AM-Softmax [41, 42] (aka CosFace loss) revised ASoftmax loss by replacing $\psi(\theta_{y_i})$ with $(\cos \theta_{y_i} - m)$, and normalizing $\|\mathbf{x}_i\| = 1$ to propose additive cosine margin loss as follows:

$$L_{\text{AMSoftmax}} = -\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \log \frac{e^{s \cdot (\cos \theta_{y_i} - m)}}{e^{s \cdot (\cos \theta_{y_i} - m)} + \sum_{j=1, j \neq y_i}^C e^{s \cdot \cos \theta_j}} \quad (2)$$

where s is a scaling factor for preventing very small gradients during the training process.

195 ArcFace [5, 21] replaced cosine margin with angular margin to enhance angular discrimination.

$$L_{\text{ArcFace}} = -\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \log \frac{e^{s(\cos(\theta_{y_i} + m))}}{e^{s(\cos(\theta_{y_i} + m))} + \sum_{j=1, j \neq y_i}^C e^{s \cos \theta_j}} \quad (3)$$

ASoftmax, AM-Softmax, and ArcFace attempt to import the angular decision margin between classes and minimize the intra-class variance through three different types of margin penalty, i.e., multiplicative angular margin, additive cosine margin, and additive angular margin, respectively. AM-Softmax expands the inter-class distance by adding cosine margin, while ArcFace moves the additive cosine margin into angular space to enforce the intra-class compactness by penalising the target logit. Thus, the intra-class compactness and inter-class diversity do not occur simultaneously. To increase the inter-class distance and achieve intra-class compactness, we propose a novel loss function called additive cosine margin loss (ACML), which not only performs best in fashion style recognition, but also competes with other angular margin-based loss functions in common classification problems.

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3 The Proposed Approach

3.1 Additive Cosine Margin Loss (ACML)

210 The most widely used loss function for classification is Softmax loss, which interprets the outputs as probabilities so that the posterior probability of the ground-truth class is maximal. For an input feature vector \mathbf{x}_i with label y_i , the softmax loss is defined as:

$$L_{\text{softmax}} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N -\log p_i = -\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \log \frac{e^{\mathbf{w}_{y_i}^T \mathbf{x}_i + b_{y_i}}}{\sum_{j=1}^C e^{\mathbf{w}_j^T \mathbf{x}_i + b_j}}, \quad (4)$$

where p_i denotes the posterior probability of \mathbf{x}_i being correctly classified into class y_i , $\mathbf{x}_i \in \mathbb{R}^d$ denotes the deep features of the i -th sample, belonging to the y_i -th class, \mathbf{w}_j

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Figure 1: Training CNNs for fashion style recognition supervised by the ACML loss. By the feature and weight normalisation, we get the $\cos \theta_j$ (logit) for each class. We add inter-class margin penalty m on the ground truth of each class ($\cos(\theta_{y_i})$). Afterwards, we calculate the $\arccos(\cos(\theta_{y_i}) - m)$ to find the angle between the feature \mathbf{x}_i and weight $\cos(\theta_{y_i}) - m$. Then, we add additive intra-class angular mini-margin penalty m^* on the distinct target angle θ_{t_i} of class y_i . After that, we calculate $\cos(\theta_{t_i} + m^*)$ and multiply all logits by the feature scale s . Finally, the logits are passed to the softmax function.

denotes the j -th column of the weight $\mathbf{W} \in \mathbb{R}^{d \times C}$ and $b_j \in \mathbb{R}^C$ is the bias term. N and C are the batch size and the class number, respectively.

The softmax loss function does not perform well in explicitly optimizing feature embedding to enforce higher similarity for intra-class samples and greater diversity for inter-class samples [39]. This leads to a performance gap in deep fashion style detection for large intra-class appearance variations (due to the high degree of variability and inconsistency) and small inter-class appearance variations (different styles look similar in some poses and under variable illumination).

Following [41, 42], we remove the bias term for simplicity, and fix $\|\mathbf{w}_j\| = 1$ and $\|\mathbf{x}_i\| = s$ by l_2 normalization to transform the logit [29] as:

$$\mathbf{w}_j^T \mathbf{x}_i = \|\mathbf{w}_j\| \|\mathbf{x}_i\| \cos \theta_j = s \cos \theta_j, \quad (5)$$

where θ_j is the angle between the weight vector \mathbf{w}_j and the feature \mathbf{x}_i . By normalizing features and weights, the posterior probability depends only on the cosine of the angle between the feature and the weight. The modified loss function can be formulated as:

$$L_{Norm} = -\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \log \frac{e^{s \cos \theta_{y_i}}}{e^{s \cos \theta_{y_i}} + \sum_{j=1, j \neq y_i}^C e^{s \cos \theta_j}}. \quad (6)$$

Since L_{Norm} only emphasizes the high similarity of features of the same class, it
 230 does not have sufficient discriminative power. To increase adequately discriminative
 power of L_{Norm} , AM-Softmax introduces the margin m from a cosine perspective to
 the classification boundary of L_{Norm} to reinforce the discrimination of learned fea-
 tures. AM-Softmax tries to magnify the distances between the true class and other
 classes which expands the inter-class distance and compresses intra-class variance to
 235 some extent.

$$L_{AM-Softmax} = -\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \log \frac{e^{s(\cos \theta_{y_i} - m)}}{e^{s(\cos \theta_{y_i} - m)} + \sum_{j=1, j \neq y_i}^C e^{s \cos \theta_j}}. \quad (7)$$

The performance of AM-Softmax is highly dependent on the best margin m , which
 is difficult to predict and fine-tune. Choosing an inappropriate margin would increase
 the intra-class variance and degrade the performance. Therefore, the best margin m
 for different computer vision problems is not stable and is determined exclusively for
 240 a specific problem, which is very time-consuming.

To deal with this issue, we do not exactly look for the best margin m in the the range
 $[0, 0.45]$ [41, 42], but we determine a rough and small m , such as the one proposed by
 AM-Softmax, and then try to reduce the intra-class variance by a mini-margin, leading
 to the convergence of the training procedure.

245 After transforming the logit and expands the inter-class distance by additive inter-
 class cosine margin penalty on target (ground truth), we calculate the corresponding
 angle between the feature \mathbf{x}_i and the distinct ground truth weight vector by taking the
 inverse of $\cos(\theta_{y_i}) - m$. This angle is given by:

$$\theta_{t_i} = \arccos(\cos(\theta_{y_i}) - m), \quad (8)$$

where $\cos(\theta_{y_i}) - m \in [-1, 1]$. Then, inspired by ArcFace loss, we add additive
 250 intra-class angular mini-margin penalty m^* to this distinct target angle θ_{t_i} of class
 y_i to simultaneously enhance the intra-class compactness. After that, we calculate
 $\cos(\theta_{t_i} + m^*)$ and multiply all logits by the feature scale s .

Finally, the additive cosine margin loss (ACML) can be formulated as:

$$L_{ACML} = -\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \log \frac{e^{s(\cos(\theta_{t_i} + m^*))}}{e^{s(\cos(\theta_{t_i} + m^*))} + \sum_{j=1, j \neq y_i}^C e^{s \cos \theta_j}}. \quad (9)$$

A schematic illustration of the main steps of the proposed ACML loss is presented in Figure 1. It is worth noting that if the margin m is set to zero the proposed ACML loss will reduce to the ArcFace loss. Furthermore, if the mini-margin m^* is set to zero the ACML loss will reduce to the AM-Softmax loss.

3.2 Theoretical Analysis for ACML

In the case of a binary classification problem, we have two classes (class 1 and class 2) whose samples are distributed on a hypersphere based on the center and feature normalization [5], as shown in Figure 2. In order to learn the discriminative features on the hypersphere and improve the intra-class compactness within the class and the discrepancy between the classes, the cosine margin serves as an important component to strengthen the discriminative power of the features. Let \mathbf{x} be the normalized feature vector of a sample in class 1, \mathbf{w}_i be the normalized class weight vector, and θ_i be the angle between \mathbf{x} and \mathbf{w}_i , $i \in \{1, 2\}$. In the normalized version of the softmax loss (Norm-Softmax), the decision boundary is defined as $\cos \theta_1 - \cos \theta_2 = 0$. This means that the decision boundary is equal to the bisector of \mathbf{w}_1 and \mathbf{w}_2 . Norm-softmax-based supervised model partitions the underlying feature space into two nearby regions that are indistinguishable (i.e., no decision boundary). Features near the decision boundary are extremely ambiguous and can belong to either class. In contrast, ACML tries to find a decision margin to strengthen the distinctiveness of the features. First, ACML controls the decision boundary for class 1 formulated by $\cos \theta_1 - m = \cos \theta_2$. This makes θ_1 much smaller than θ_2 (similarly for class 2). Consequently, the variance between classes (in angle space) is increased according to the margin m . To further reduce θ_1 and thus reduce the within-class variance of class 1, ACML computes θ_t by inverting $\cos \theta_1 - m$, where θ_1 is smaller than θ_t . Then, the additive, intra-class mini-margin penalty m^* is added to θ_t by $\theta_t + m^*$. Applying the mini-margin penalty m^* to θ_t makes it smaller (after loss optimization) and the corresponding cosine value larger, resulting in θ_1 being smaller than before. Since the inter-class margin penalty m is

Figure 2: Based on the center and feature normalization, class1 and class2 are distributed on a hypersphere. Different ellipses represent feature space from distinct classes. Dashed lines represent decision boundaries, and white area in ACML (margin) is the decision margin. \mathbf{x}_1 is the normalized feature vector of class1. \mathbf{w}_i and θ_i denote the normalized weight vector and the angle between \mathbf{x}_1 and \mathbf{w}_i , respectively. ACML has a relatively compact feature region compared with Norm-Softmax.

constant, increasing the value of $\cos \theta_t = \cos \theta_1 - m$ (by using m^*) means decreasing the angle θ_1 . The above reasoning applies similarly to class2. Thus, ACML strengthens the discrimination of the learned features by increasing the variance between classes and decreasing the variance within classes. The above analysis generalizes well to the scenario with multiple classes.

3.3 Geometric Difference of ACML with AM-Softmax and ArcFace

To make it easier to understand the difference between our method and most important margin based Softmax losses i.e. AM-softmax and ArcFace, we discuss the decision boundaries of different losses for binary classification in Figure 3. Compared to previous works, the proposed ACML has a better geometric decision margins. Despite the ArcFace has a constant linear angular margin when the \mathbf{x}_i deviates too much from the center \mathbf{w}_{y_i} [20], an overlap area will occur where can be considered as class 1 and class 2. AM-softmax has only a nonlinear angular margin which is not sufficient for compactness within a class. First, using a nonlinear angular margin, ACML establishes an appropriate margin between classes to ensure that there is no area of overlap between classes. Then, using a constant linear angular mini-margin leads to better intra-class compactness. Therefore, the proposed ACML loss jointly retains the strengths of AM-Softmax and ArcFace losses and avoids their limitations.

Figure 3: Decision margins of different loss functions in the case of binary classification. The dashed line indicates the decision boundary, and the white areas are the decision margin. The grey area is the overlap area of class 1 and class 2.

In Figure 4, we show the target logit curves of SphereFace ($m = 1.35$), AM-
 300 Softmax ($m = 0.35$), ArcFace ($m = 0.50$) and ACML ($m = 0.35, m^* = 0.05$) under
 their best margin settings. For these margin settings and for small angles (classification
 can be certain) the logit associated with ACML is close to those of AM-Softmax and
 ArcFace. For large angles, the logit of ACML tends to be between those of the standard
 Softmax and the AM-Softmax.

305 Considering the gradient value of the target logit curves of different losses, we can
 see the target logit of ACML loss function will not decline rapidly compare to AM-
 Softmax and ArcFace which makes the proposed loss function perform better.

4 Performance evaluation

4.1 Datasets

310 Our empirical validation was performed on the HipsterWars [17] and Fashion-
 Style14 [37] datasets to investigate the effectiveness of our method in detecting fashion
 styles. The HipsterWars dataset consists of 1,893 images related to five fashion styles:
 Bohemian, Goth, Hipster, Pinup, and Preppy. To indicate the strength of reflection of
 each fashion style by an image, each image has been assigned a confidence score of
 315 0 to 50. The FashionStyle14 dataset consists of 13,126 images related to 14 fashion
 styles: conservative, dressy, ethnic, fairy, feminine, gal, girlish, casual, lolita, mode,
 natural, retro, rock, and street. The styles are annotated by fashion experts.

Figure 4: Target logit curves for Softmax, SphereFace, AM-Softmax, ArcFace and ACML (proposed).

We also compared the performance of the proposed ACML on efficient face verification and recognition datasets. We use CASIA [49] and MS1MV2 [5] separately as training data to allow fair comparison with other methods. CASIA contains 494,414 face images belonging to 10,575 different individuals. The MS1MV2 dataset is a semi-automated, refined version of the MSCeleb-1M dataset [11], which contains 5.8 million face images belonging to 85,742 different individuals. The test datasets we used are the LFW [14], YTF [46], and MegaFace [16] datasets. LFW and YTF are the two most widely used datasets for unconstrained face verification. The LFW dataset contains 13,233 face images of 5749 identities collected from some websites, and the YTF dataset contains 3,425 videos of 1,595 different people collected from YouTube, with an average of 2 videos per identity.

MegaFace is a highly challenging dataset released for face identification and verification. The MegaFace dataset includes gallery and probe sets. The gallery and probe sets contain 1 million images of 690,000 different people and 100,000 images of 530 unique people from FaceScrub, respectively.

4.2 Experimental Settings

In the experiment with the HipsterWars dataset, according to a previous study [48],
335 we used only the images that had a confidence score of at least 50%. We also divided
the selected images into training, validation, and test sets in a ratio of 8:1:1. To ensure
a fair comparison, the split between training, validation, and testing is given for the
FashionStyle14 dataset [37] (60% of the dataset for training, 5% of the dataset for vali-
dation, and 35% of the dataset for testing). Consistent with the state of the art, we used
340 this split in all of our experiments. In both dataset experiments, the images are resized
to 214×474 before inputting into the deep neural networks. Since fashion images
across different datasets have different brightness, contrast, sharpness, quality of align-
ment, in order to improve the generalization ability of our model, data augmentation is
performed.

345 To verify the benefit of the proposed loss function, we enlisted five of the most well-
known network architectures: ResNet50, MobileNetV2, InceptionResNetV2, DenseNet121
and DenseNet169. While DenseNet121 and DenseNet169 consist of the DenseBlocks
with varying number of layers, ResNet50, MobileNetV2 and InceptionResNetV2 are
made up of residual blocks in which information flow is enhanced by an identity map-
ping from early layers. We trained CNNs on the training sets and tuned the margin
350 parameters m (for AM-Softmax and ArcFace) and m^* (for ACML) on the validation
sets of the two datasets. We fine-tune a model that has been trained on the ImageNet
dataset 1000-class classification problem. For fine-tuning, we replace the top layers
by a global average pooling layer. We optimized the multinomial cross-entropy loss
355 between the activation outputs and ground truth labels using Adam. We considered
softmax, Norm-softmax, AM-softmax, ArcFace and ACML as loss functions. Test
data were used to evaluate classification accuracy. We report classification accuracy as
well class-wise accuracy. The implementation of our method is based on Tensorflow
1.15 with NVIDIA GTX 2080i GPU. The hyper parameters of ACML is set as follows:
360 $m = 0.35, s = 64, m^* = 0.05$. The feature norm s should be large enough to ensure
an adequate hyperspace for feature learning. Empirically, it does not have much effect
on performance. The CNN models are optimized with the batch size of 64 on a single
GPU, and the weight decay is fixed to be 1×10^{-5} .

4.3 Ablation Study for Pre-trained Models and AM-softmax and ArcFace Losses

365 First, we perform an ablation study on the HipsterWars and FashionStyle14 datasets to investigate the improvements made by CNN models pre-trained on the ImageNet dataset. We chose five different backbone CNNs, i.e., InceptionResNetV2, ResNet50, MobileNetV2, DenseNet121 and DenseNet169. The standard Softmax was adopted to analyze the role of network architectures in improvement. To avoid misleading for
370 a wrong sense of robustness, we performed an empirical study to evaluate the per-class accuracy along with the global accuracy of trained models. The classification accuracies and per-class accuracies for different fashion styles with various pre-trained models are reported in Tables 2 and 3. It is obvious that DenseNet169 has the best performance in both datasets. Moreover, we have conducted extensive experiments (Table 4)
375 on the loss functions AM-Softmax, and ArcFace with DenseNet169 pre-trained model to show that the best margins proposed in the original papers are not stable for different computer vision problems and were obtained exclusively for a specific problem. AM-Softmax and ArcFace were proposed with margin values of 0.35 and 0.50, respectively, for the face recognition problem. From Table 4, we can see that the best
380 performances of AM-Softmax and ArcFace methods are obtained with margin values of 0.45 and 0.40 for FashionStyle14 dataset and 0.30 and 0.40 for HipsterWars dataset, respectively. From this experiment, we can see that the AM-Softmax and ArcFace performances highly depend on the best margin.

4.4 Effect of m^*

385 To investigate the important role of the mini-margin m^* in ACML, we evaluated the effect of m^* by an experiment in this part. In Figure 5, we see that a mini-margin m^* leads to a more discriminative distribution in the feature space. When no mini-margin is applied ($m^* = 0$), we do not use ACML, i.e., we train directly with AM-Softmax with a margin of 0.35. When m^* increases from 1×10^{-2} to 5×10^{-2} (if m^* is larger
390 than 9×10^{-2} , the model does not converge), the accuracy improves from 88.25% to 90.0% on HipsterWars dataset, and the accuracy on FashionStyle14 dataset has an increase from 84.95% to 89.61%. When the mini-margin is set too large (larger than 5×10^{-2}), the recognition accuracy will have a slight degradation.

Table 2: Per-class accuracy (%) and global accuracy obtained by different CNNs on the HipsterWars dataset. The best results are shown in bold. The results correspond to the standard Softmax loss.

Model	Bohemian	Goth	Hipster	Pinup	Preppy	All
InceptionResNetV2	67.36	79.26	56.28	67.18	65.52	67.36
ResNet50	80.27	83.26	57.10	69.20	66.86	71.57
MobileNetV2	76.36	86.08	57.42	69.16	65.07	71.05
DenseNet121	81.81	89.56	54.21	76.16	62.63	73.68
DenseNet169	84.54	90.43	60.23	76.51	69.36	76.31

Table 3: Per-class accuracy (%) and global accuracy obtained by different CNNs on the FashionStyle14 dataset. The best results are shown in bold. The results correspond to the standard Softmax loss.

Model \ Class	InceptionResNetV2	ResNet50	MobileNetV2	DenseNet121	DenseNet169
conserv.	53.00	60.07	60.07	67.13	65.93
dressy	60.48	96.77	96.77	90.21	88.70
ethnic	89.70	79.73	89.70	83.05	96.34
fairy	61.81	80.31	75.12	89.94	90.31
feminine	51.63	59.78	58.91	68.50	68.91
gal	64.28	75.00	77.14	77.85	80.71
girlish	49.05	39.85	50.24	52.39	62.12
casual	57.62	64.40	71.18	54.23	64.40
lolita	95.50	98.31	92.69	92.69	92.07
mode	74.85	74.85	68.86	80.83	74.85
natural	63.69	70.06	63.69	70.06	70.06
retro	62.30	56.07	52.29	68.53	62.30
rock	58.28	64.41	65.34	78.07	69.07
street	49.83	66.44	63.15	69.80	67.12
All	63.49	70.55	70.85	74.28	75.23

4.5 Evaluation Results

395 4.5.1 Experiments with Baseline Losses

In Tables 5 and 6, we compare the performance of ACML with the state-of-the-art margin-based softmax losses. For better evaluation, we implement the Norm-Softmax loss, AM-Softmax loss [42], SphereFace loss [23], and ArcFace loss [5]. The best pre-trained model (DenseNet169) was trained with these loss functions on both datasets
400 (FashionStyle14 and HipsterWars). We compared the classification accuracies (all) and per-class accuracies for different fashion styles. As can be seen in Tables 5 and 6, the model supervised by ACML outperforms the other loss functions in global classification accuracy and some class-related accuracies. ACML achieves a classification ac-

Table 4: Classification accuracy (%) of AM-Softmax and ArcFace with different margins on FashionStyle14 and HipsterWars.

Loss Function \ m	0.10	0.15	0.20	0.25	0.30	0.35	0.40	0.45	0.50	0.55
FashionStyle14										
AM-Softmax	81.72	83.86	84.70	85.03	85.17	84.95	85.28	85.30	85.08	83.22
ArcFace	80.39	81.78	82.39	83.78	84.19	85.23	85.73	85.26	84.74	84.24
HipsterWars										
AM-Softmax	80.12	85.96	86.79	87.73	88.42	88.25	87.38	86.66	85.58	84.92
ArcFace	81.33	82.68	83.79	85.88	87.29	87.63	87.89	87.34	86.84	82.94

Figure 5: Accuracy (%) of ACML with different mini-margin parameters m^* on HipsterWars and FashionStyle14 datasets.

Table 5: Comparison between the per-class accuracy and all accuracy values of different loss functions in the HipsterWars dataset. The best results are shown in bold.

Loss Function	Bohemian	Goth	Hipster	Pinup	Preppy	All
Norm-Softmax	88.18	96.08	70.00	63.84	57.55	75.26
SphereFace	77.27	89.13	81.57	67.89	76.74	78.94
AM-Softmax	90.90	97.82	86.84	70.63	93.02	88.42
ArcFace	86.38	95.65	81.57	78.94	90.69	87.89
ACML (ours)	88.63	95.65	86.84	78.42	97.67	90.00

Table 6: Comparison between the per-class accuracy and all accuracy values of different loss functions in the FashionStyle14 dataset. The best results are shown in bold.

Class \ Loss Function	Norm-Softmax	SphereFace	AM-Softmax	ArcFace	ACML (ours)
conserv.	65.86	89.38	82.62	86.59	81.45
dressy	84.24	83.33	98.76	80.98	94.18
ethnic	67.38	76.60	89.64	89.29	94.60
fairy	88.13	91.52	88.13	81.18	84.40
feminine	79.64	76.66	94.73	87.19	90.17
gal	76.51	76.44	83.12	89.83	86.44
girlish	78.80	72.50	79.78	83.80	88.80
casual	80.83	83.89	76.88	70.86	85.86
lolita	90.63	95.27	95.48	78.54	91.57
mode	66.44	86.37	86.37	86.51	86.37
natural	74.93	69.43	81.67	84.59	93.02
retro	64.51	67.20	80.64	89.89	86.82
rock	76.53	79.20	82.40	94.60	88.86
street	66.87	71.87	73.69	90.06	90.98
All	76.13	80.16	85.30	85.73	89.61

accuracy of 90.00% (all) on the HipsterWars dataset, which is an improvement of 2.11%
 405 over ArcFace. In addition, ACML improves the per-class accuracy for the Hipster and
 Preppy classes. For the other fashion style classes in the HipsterWars dataset, ACML
 is in close competition with ArcFace and AM-Softmax. As we discussed in Section
 4.3, AM-Softmax and ArcFace depend heavily on the value of their margin penalties.
 We found that AM-Softmax and ArcFace perform best in the HipsterWars dataset with
 410 a margin of 0.30 and 0.40, respectively. With the best margin of 0.30, AM-Softmax
 improves the discrepancy between classes for the Bohemian and Goth fashion styles,
 while it reduces the compactness between classes for the Pinup class. ArcFace, with
 a margin of 0.40, improves the compactness within classes for the Pinup class, but
 performs poorly on inter-class discrepancy for the Bohemian, Goth, and Hipster fash-
 415 ion styles. Unlike AM-Softmac and ArcFace, ACML increases the variance between
 classes while decreasing the variance within classes. This advantage of ACML is most
 evident in the Preppy class, which requires simultaneous within-class compactness and
 between-class discrepancy. In the FashionStyle14 dataset, ACML achieves a classifi-
 cation accuracy of 89.61% (all), an improvement of 3.88% over ArcFace. As shown
 420 in Table 6, AM-Softmax with 85.30% and ArcFace with 85.73% classification accu-

accuracy are almost equal, indicating that compactness within classes and diversity between classes do not occur simultaneously. ACML has a more balanced performance than the other losses in per-class accuracy. ACML achieves 94.60% and 81.45% accuracy for ethnic and conservative classes as the best and worst performance, respectively. This means that the difference between the best and worst performance of ACML is 13.15%,
425 while this value is 28.07%, 25.07% and 23.74% for SphereFace, AM-Softmax and ArcFace, respectively. Some classes require either intra-class compactness or inter-class discrepancy, while some of them require both. AM-Softmax puts more emphasis on widening the discrepancy between classes, while SphereFace and ArcFace improve
430 intra-class compactness. From Table 6, we can see that SphereFace has the best accuracy for conservative and fairy classes, but the worst for some classes (e.g., ethnic, natural, retro, etc.), suggesting that SphereFace does not work well for some classes that require discrepancy between classes. The situation is similar for AM-Softmax and ArcFace. ACML simultaneously enforces compactness within a class and diversity
435 between classes, resulting in more balanced performance than other losses. ACML achieves the best accuracy for the ethnic, girlish, casual, natural, and street classes, but also competes closely with SphereFace, AM-Softmax, and ArcFace for the other fashion style classes. To get a better understanding of ACML’s superiority, we compared the bidimensional embeddings resulting from the ACML and from the state-of-
440 the-art losses, in the FashionStyle14 dataset (Figure 6). This plot yielded from the projection of a 128-dimensional embedding down to two dimensions, according to the t-distributed stochastic neighbor embedding (t-SNE) algorithm [38]. It can be seen that from the softmax to AM-Softmax loss, the inter-class discrepancy is increased. Since the AM-Softmax focuses on inter-class, intra-class variations can not effectively
445 compress. This leads to overlap between some classes and eventually decreasing the discriminative power. Although ArcFace has good intra-class compactness, it does not address inter-class, simultaneously. ArcFace enforces the intra-class compactness and inter-class diversity is increased to some extent. In contrast to ArcFace, ACML with a simultaneous focus on inter-class discrepancy and intra-class variations achieves a
450 high discriminative power.

In Figure 7, we draw the Receiver Operating Characteristic curves (ROC) to eval-

455 uate the performance of recognition on FashionStyle14 and HipsterWars datasets. The curves of the AM-Softmax and the ArcFace are close together which comes from their exclusive emphasis on inter-class or intra-class distances. Considering both inter-class and intra-class distances at the same time, ACML shows superiority over state-of-the-art losses and forms an upper envelope of ArcFace using the DenseNet169 architecture.

Figure 6: Comparison between the t-SNE embeddings resulting from the baseline losses, and from the proposed ACML loss (last plot) on the FashionStyle14 dataset.

4.5.2 Comparison with state-of-the-art Methods

Two latest works, Nakajima et al. [25] and Yamamoto et al. [48] are the state-of-the-art works for fashion style recognition, which are conducted on the HipsterWars

Figure 7: Comparison between the Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curves observed for the a) FashionStyle14 and b) HipsterWars datasets, using the DenseNet169 architecture. Results are shown for the ACML loss function, and four baselines: Norm Softmax, SphereFace, AM-Softmax and ArcFace.

460 and FashionStyle14 datasets and achieved best performances. Table 7 summarizes the performance of the state-of-the-art methods and ACML on the HipsterWars and FashionStyle14 datasets. Nakajima et al. used SSD for human body detection and PSPNet for semantic segmentation. Then, they applied ResNet-50 which trained with the WEARStyle dataset, to extract features and achieved 80.9% accuracy on the HipsterWars dataset. Yamamoto et al. created six component images from an input image by JPPNet and DeepLabv3+. Then, they extracted features of each component by component-dependent convolutional neural networks (CD-CNNs) based on pre-trained ResNet-50. They performed the classification using extracted features by CD-CNNs with a support vector machine (SVM) as a classifier. They found the best performance through four components and six components as feature combinations for the HipsterWars and FashionStyle14 datasets. These methods attempt to strengthen feature embedding by using complex scenarios and huge deep learning models to support effective learning, while using a softmax loss function that does not perform well in explicit feature embedding optimization to enforce higher similarity for intra-class samples and greater diversity for inter-class samples. As we can see, compared to the other methods, ACML shows superior recognition outcomes on HipsterWars dataset. Compared to 4-component combination method, using ACML the accuracy of the deep model improved by approximately 5%. Also, ACML has a better performance compared to AM-Softmax and ArcFace methods. The differences of loss functions contributed

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480 to these improvements. Our method achieved 90.0% accuracy with DenseNet169 and 4.7% improvement on HipsterWars compared with the best of state-of-the-art methods.

Table 7 also shows the classification accuracy of the baseline approaches and our approach for the FashionStyle14 dataset. The higher accuracy of the DenseNet169 model with ACML shows that our method outperforms the baseline approaches in the 485 test set. AM-Softmax and ArcFace could improve the performance of deep model 8%, approximately. Our method achieved 89.61% accuracy, a 11.91% improvement compared with 6-component combination method. However, there are some noisy tags (e.g. 'thickness of clothes') in FashionStyle14 dataset, therefore, if these tags / attributes are filtered, we expect to see better performance. Moreover, unlike the 490 state-of-the-art network design, we only use a typical CNN architecture supervised by ACML to achieve this performance. Note that the contribution of the 6-component combination method is to use both global and local representations, which is orthogonal to our method. Of course, we can use feature embedding techniques to further improve our model.

Table 7: Accuracy (%) of state-of-the-art methods on HipsterWars and FashionStyle14 datasets.

Method	HipsterWars	FashionStyle14
Kiapour et al. [17]	70.6	-
StyleNet [33]	75.9	-
Nakajima et al. [25]	80.9	-
Takagi et al. [37]	-	72.0
1-component[48]	83.0	75.5
2-component[48]	84.2	75.9
3-component[48]	84.3	76.9
4-component[48]	85.3	77.3
5EL [48]	85.1	77.4
5EP [48]	85.0	77.6
6-component[48]	84.5	77.7
AM-Softmax	88.42	85.30
ArcFace	87.89	85.73
ACML (ours)	90.0	89.61

495 *4.6 Face verification and identification*

For further comparison and demonstration the efficiency of the proposed method in extracting deep features. we conducted face verification and identification experiments on LFW, YTF and MegaFace datasets and compared our results with the performance of the state-of-the-art methods.

500 LFW and YTF datasets are the most widely used benchmark for unconstrained face verification on images and videos. For a fair comparison, we follow the *unrestricted with labelled outside data* protocol to report the performance. In accordance with [5], We used ResNet100 as CNN architecture and trained it on the MS1MV2 dataset as training data supervised by ACML loss. Then, we performed model evaluations on LFW and YTF testing sets.

As can be seen from Table 8, the proposed ACML achieves state-of-the-art results of 99.91% on LFW and 99.25% on YTF, which demonstrates the effectiveness of ACML to enhance the discriminative power of deeply learned features. CosFace (AM-softmax) increases the inter-class variance by adding a cosine margin, while ArcFace 510 moves the additive cosine margin into angle space to improve intra-class compactness. By using the additive inter-class cosine margin and the additive angle mini-span, ACML increases the inter-class variance while further decreasing the intra-class variance. For further evaluation, we compare ACML performance on MegaFace dataset. MegaFace is a highly challenging dataset which is released for face identification and 515 verification. In MegaFace, identification and verification testing scenarios are defined under large and small training set protocols. The difference between small and large protocols is that the small training protocol has less than 0.5 million images. For a fair comparison, we train ResNet100 with ACML on CAISA and MS1MV2 datasets for the small and large protocols. Table 9 summarizes the results of our method trained on two protocols. As can be seen, ACML achieves the best identification and verification 520 performance on both protocols and outperforms other methods.

4.7 Statistical Analysis

Statistical analysis of the results can be gotten by playing out the Friedman test [4]. This test is utilized to compare the average ranks of different algorithms. The null

Table 8: Verification performance (%) of different methods on LFW and YTF.

Loss Functions	LFW	YTF
DeepID [35]	99.47	93.20
Deep Face [36]	97.35	91.40
VGG Face [26]	98.95	97.30
FaceNet [31]	99.63	95.10
Center Loss [45]	99.28	94.90
Range Loss [51]	99.52	93.70
Marginal Loss [6]	99.48	95.98
SphereFace [23]	99.42	95.00
CosFace[42]	99.73	97.60
ArcFace[5]	99.83	98.02
ACML (ours)	99.91	99.25

Table 9: Identification and verification evaluation on MegaFace Challenge1. Identification refers to the rank 1 face identification accuracy with 1M distractors, and Verification refers to the face verification TAR under $1e - 6$ FAR.

Methods	Protocol	Identification (%)	Verification (%)
Softmax [23]	Small	54.85	65.92
Contrastive Loss [23, 35]	Small	65.21	78.86
Triplet Loss [23, 31]	Small	64.79	78.32
Center Loss[45]	Small	65.49	80.14
SphereFace [23]	Small	72.73	85.56
CosFace[42]	Small	77.11	89.88
AM-Softmax[41]	Small	72.47	84.44
ArcFace [5]	Small	77.50	92.34
ACML (ours)	Small	79.80	93.47
FaceNet[31]	Large	70.49	86.47
CosFace[42]	Large	82.72	96.65
ArcFace [5]	Large	81.03	96.98
ACML (ours)	Large	83.16	97.66

525 hypothesis states that all the algorithms are equivalent, and thus, their ranks should be equal. If the null hypothesis is rejected, one can perform a post-hoc test (the Nemenyi test) to find out which algorithms significantly differ. Since we only have results of four margin-based softmax losses (i.e. ACML, ArcFace, AM-Softmax, and SphereFace) on all datasets (i.e. fashion style, face verification and identification datasets), we compare

530 the average ranks of these losses. The Friedman test (run on the average rank of the four methods) stated that the performance of all four methods is not the same. The Critical Distance CD is computed [4]. In our case, we have a total of four methods including ACML, ArcFace, AM-Softmax, and SphereFace with 5 evaluations. Figure 8 shows the CD diagram for the four methods, where the average rank of each is marked in front of them.

535 The CD diagram allows to have groups of methods that are significantly different. To further analyze the obtained results and draw clear conclusions, we perform the Wilcoxon rank sum test. We use the Wilcoxon rank sum test and assume a confidence level of 90% (i.e., we consider a statistical significance threshold of $p < 0.1$). Table 10 illustrates the results of the Wilcoxon test for the performances

540 presented in Tables 5 and 6. Each cell in the table corresponds to a comparison between the proposed ACML method and a particular competing method. The symbol (\checkmark) means that the proposed method (ACML) has a significant improvement over the corresponding competing method. The symbol (\equiv) means that there is no statistical evidence that the method outperforms the competing method.

Figure 8: CD diagram of margin-based Softmax methods.

545 5 Conclusion and future work

In this paper, we propose a novel additive cosine margin loss (ACML) for deep learning architectures that enables models to derive more effective and discriminative

Table 10: Statistical significance of the proposed method using Wilcoxon method with 90% confidence level (i.e., the p-value is set to 0.1). The symbol (\checkmark) means that the proposed loss function (ACML) significantly improves over the corresponding competing loss function. The symbol (\equiv) indicates that there is no statistical evidence that the method outperforms the compared method.

Method \ Dataset	HipsterWars	FashionStyle14
SphereFace	\checkmark	\checkmark
AM-Softmax	\equiv	\checkmark
ArcFace	\checkmark	\checkmark

representations for the fashion style and face recognition problems. ACML takes advantage of inter-class separation and intra-class compactness by adding an additive angle mini-margin to the target angle associated with the cosine margin. In the proposed loss function, the cosine margin expands the inter-class distance, then the additive intra-class angular mini-margin penalty is added to enhance the intra-class compactness. Unlike margin-based softmax losses, where intra-class compactness and inter-class diversity do not occur simultaneously, our loss function not only enforces separability between different classes but also favors compact representations within each class, which contributed to the observed good performance. The results of the comparisons also show the competitive performance of the proposed loss function compared to state-of-the-art methods based on Deep Learning on the well-known fashion style recognition datasets FashionStyle14 and HipsterWars, and on the face verification and identification datasets LFW, YTF, and MegaFace. Our proposed method achieves a classification accuracy of 90.0% and 89.61% on the HipsterWars and FashionStyle14 datasets, respectively, and improves the classification accuracy by 4.7% and 11.91% over all competitors. Moreover, the proposed ACML achieves top results of 99.91% in LFW and 99.25% in YTF, demonstrating the effectiveness of ACML in improving the distinctiveness of deep learned features. In this study, we only use a typical CNN architecture supervised by ACML to achieve these performances. Our future research avenue is to improve the proposed method in terms of using feature embedding techniques.

Conflict of Interest Statement

570 The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

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